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POLITICAL CULTURE AS A CONDITION FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF TRADITIONALISM OF POWER AND MANAGEMENT IN THE PRC

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Abstract. The article focuses on the phenomenon of political culture as an important condition in the development of the external and internal potential of the state. The transformation processes of the vital goals of the country's party building are studied.

Key words: political culture, power, governance, political system, socialism with Chinese characteristics.

Innovations in power and administration in the PRC at the current stage are associated with the following political and cultural reconstructions. There is a significant breakthrough in the comprehensive deepening of reforms, active and sustainable progress of reforms aimed at eliminating systemic and institutional failures in all spheres. Important steps have been taken in the formation of democracy and the legal field. In the process of forming a political system aimed at achieving socialist democracy, large-scale work was carried out on the ground. Their goal was to ensure the rule of law in public administration, to proclaim institution-building designed to preserve the organic unity of the party leadership and the position of the people as the masters of the state. Law-making, demands for fair justice and compliance with the law have intensified. From the point of view of cultural historicism, noticeable improvements are observed in the ideological work of the administrative authorities. Ideological and cultural innovations have taken place in the party leadership. In the sphere of ideology, the directive principles of Marxism are more clearly established. Socialism with Chinese characteristics and the Chinese dream have been absolutely entrenched in the minds of the people. The most important values of socialism and the optimal achievements of Chinese traditional

culture have been disseminated. Mass events aimed at the formation of spiritual culture have acquired great significance. The authorities supported social services in the field of culture, the flourishing of literature and art, and the entire cultural sphere and industry in general. The traditional cultural views of the governing authorities contributed to favorable conditions for nationwide measures to improve health and the comprehensive formation of professional sports.

The specific features of China's political culture have contributed to the manifestation of a distinctive culture with a centuries-old history based on the unity and integrity of government and society. One of the elements of political culture in China is inner-party governance, which is rooted in the Confucian theory of governance. The Party leadership has focused on instilling in its members respect for the Party Constitution, political consciousness, strengthening the Party core and equality of interests, and enhancing the prestige of the CPC Central Committee and its overall centralized leadership. At the same time, the most important values of the managerial power of the party leadership are the traditional observance of party-political discipline and ethics, and the political responsibility of everyone for internal party management.

Current trends in the country's political culture are observed in the transition to a new era of building socialism with Chinese characteristics. This means that the Chinese nation has undergone tremendous changes in the course of its socio-political, cultural and historical development: it has endured innumerable disasters, has risen to its feet, has begun to live better, and has been transformed into an intense and powerful nation that is on its way to achieving the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

The realization of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation is the greatest dream of the Chinese nation since the beginning of modern history. Since its founding, the Communist Party of China has unquestionably undertaken this historic mission and strive to carry it out. Uniting the people around itself, the Party at the same time waged a bitter struggle aimed at freeing the Chinese people from the incredible burden of the "three great mountains"—imperialism, feudalism, and

bureaucratic capitalism—and to resist it by achieving national independence and uniting the political system of the state with society [1]. The Chinese Communist Party, endowed with administrative power, found a just revolutionary path by surrounding the city with villages and declaring an armed seizure of power.

This contributed to the formation of traditional elements of political culture – the key political prerequisites for the creation of the institutional foundation of modern China. The Chinese nation has made a great leap from a situation of constant decline to a radical transformation of its destiny and a steady march towards improvement and prosperity.

Thus, modern trends in political culture have become necessary conditions for traditional power and governance in China, and have transformed the content of the vital goals of the great program of party building of the country, which the ruling party is currently following.

The historical and political transformations in China indicate that without the traditionally established format of power and control of the CPC, the revival of the nation would inevitably have collapsed. In order for the party to be recognized as the vanguard of the epoch and the main backbone of the nation, to continuously follow the ideas of Marxism, it itself needs to implement and further modify the historically laid down and time-tested traditional methods of governing power. Proof of this can be seen in the Confucian teachings on prudent principles of governance, making bold decisions, and preserving the healthy body of the party. In this regard, the best traditions of administrative power can be efforts aimed at constantly building up the party's capabilities in political leadership, ideological orientation, mass organization, and social mobilization [2].

The specific features of modern political culture as a condition for traditional administrative power in China are the ways to realize the great dream of building "socialism with Chinese characteristics." This requires a reasonable mobilization of forces, combining the party's managerial theory and the practice of political reforms, their openness, trustworthiness and suitability for achieving goals. The path of "socialism with Chinese characteristics" is the indisputable path to socialist

transformation and modernization of a comfortable life. The theoretical structure of "socialism with Chinese characteristics" is the inevitable theory that guides the Party and the people towards the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. A socialist system with Chinese characteristics is the main institutional guarantee for the formation and development of modern China. Socialist culture with Chinese characteristics is a powerful spiritual force that inspires the Party and the multi-ethnic people of China to move forward with courage.

References:

1. Aristova L.B., Semenova N.K. One Belt - One Road: Constructive and Negative Factors in the Development of Transport Dialogue in the Format of the Russian Federation - Central Asia - China [Electronic resource] // Proceedings of the IX International Scientific and Practical Conference (Blagoveshchensk–Heihe, Tianjin, Beijing, May 20-28, 2019). Issue 9. Part 7 / Editor-in-Chief: D.V. Kuznetsov. - Blagoveshchensk: Publishing house BSPU, 2019. -196 p. // Mode of access: https://bgpu.ru/newsfiles/5405_f1558051110973.pdf.
2. Report of President Xi Jinping at the XIX National Congress of the Communist Party of China [Electronic resource] // Report at the XIX National Congress of the Communist Party of China on October 18, 2017 by Xi Jinping// Mode of access: <http://md.chineseembassy.org/eng/zt/19cpc/t1507416.htm>.
3. Bokshchanin A.A. China and the Countries of the South Seas of the XIV-XVI centuries [Electronic resource] - M.: Nauka, 1968. P.23-25. // Mode of access: https://vk.com/wall-52136985_30482.
4. Sidoreyko I.V. Confucianism and Modern Political Culture of China [Electronic resource] // Journal of International Law and International Relations, № 3. 2008 // Mode of access: https://vk.com/wall-52136985_30482
https://elib.bsu.by/bitstream/123456789/19057/1/2008_3_JILIR_sidoreyko_r.pdf.

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